

The Role of Judiciary in Women Empowerment in India

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Abstract

Women's empowerment is the most effective weapon for development, according to this statement (Kofi Annan). The role of the judiciary in empowering women in India has been instrumental in addressing longstanding gender disparities and advancing women's rights. This research paper provides a concise overview of the key contributions of the Indian judiciary to women's empowerment. In a country where women have historically faced systemic discrimination and inequality, the judiciary has played a pivotal role in ensuring their rights and status are protected and elevated. Historically, India has struggled with gender-based disparities deeply rooted in societal norms and traditions. Discrimination against women in areas such as education, employment, and personal freedom was widespread. The Indian judiciary has responded by interpreting the Constitution and enacting legal reforms to promote gender equality. Landmark judgments have set crucial precedents in addressing sexual harassment and marital rape. These decisions have been pivotal in empowering women and raising awareness of their rights. The judiciary's proactive stance on women's issues, particularly through judicial activism, has been a driving force behind women's empowerment. Despite these advancements, challenges and criticisms exist. The judiciary's caseload often leads to delayed justice, and some argue that certain judgments have fallen short of addressing complex women's issues adequately. However, the overall impact of the judiciary on Indian society has been profound. The number of women in both economic and political positions has increased and gender-based violence is increasingly being addressed. This research paper concludes by emphasizing the importance of the judiciary's role in promoting women's empowerment in India. While challenges persist, the judiciary's proactive approach, landmark judgments, and legal reforms have undeniably contributed to improving the status and rights of women in the Indian. The judiciary in India stays the same a cornerstone in ongoing struggle for gender equality and women's empowerment in the nation.

Key words: Judiciary, Women Empowerment, Women's Rights, Discrimination.

Introduction

Looking at a country's women's status might reveal a lot about its health.

- Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru

The traditional Indian mindset holds that men should be the head of the home in the current state of affairs between men and women. He will provide for his family's fundamental requirements through his work and protect them. And the woman will continue to live under his husband's roof, taking care of the family by doing housework. Indian women were prohibited from working outside the home and earning money before to the British invasion. They were also not regarded as "persons." The Indian High Courts in Calcutta Regina Guha¹ and Patna Re Sudhansu Bala Hazra² denied women's applications to register under the Legal Practitioners Act. These courts' whole bench ruled that the

women did not fall within the definition of "person." In the years following the British era, women's position continued to rise. Today's world is different.

Women are accepted for leaving the house and excelling in the private and public sectors alike. Therefore, it is important to defend women's rights everywhere in society—at home, outside of the home, at work, etc. It must be ensured that there is no discrimination based on factors such as caste, creed, gender, language, etc. Equal opportunities for men and women should be provided for them in order to fulfill their potential, seek happiness, contribute toward the construction of their nation, and reap the rewards of progress and advancement. We call this gender equality. All of this would be possible if the State and those who represent it gave enough taking into account the situation of every person since equal liberated in regards to privileges, irrespective of their sex. It is critical that judges are cognizant aware of and sympathetic to the issue of gender prejudice because women often turn to the legal system for protection and justice when they are victims of abuse, discrimination, or violence.³

UNFPA guidelines state that "the empowerment of women comprises five components: women's sense of self-worth; their rights to have and determine choices; their right to access resources and opportunities; their respective positions right to have the power to control their personal lives, both inside and outside the home; and their ability to impact directions of changes in society to create more just economic and social conditions on national and international levels."⁴

Women empowerment is a procedure that allows women to take charge of their own affairs and make choices that will impact them. It is about enabling women to have equal access to opportunities and resources, and to be free from violence and discrimination. The judiciary plays an important role in empowering women in India by interpreting and applying the law in a way that protects and promotes their rights. All Indian citizens are guaranteed equality under the Constitution, regardless of their gender. However, Indian women are still confronted with discrimination and inequality in a variety of life domains. The Courts has played a significant role in addressing these issues by issuing landmark judgments that have expanded the scope of the freedoms and rights of women. Among the most important contributions from the courts to women empowerment has been the recognition of the equality right. Within the historic *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India*⁵, The Supreme Court ruled that one of the fundamental rights protected by the fourteenth article of the Constitution of India is the right to equality. This right encompasses the freedom from sex-based discrimination as well as the privilege of treatment with respect and dignity. Also, the judiciary has participated in an important part in shielding women from abuse and discrimination. In the case of *Vishakha* ⁶, The Supreme Court established rules for the prevention of workplace sexual harassment. These guidelines have been instrumental in creating a safer environment for women at work. The court has also stepped in to defend women's rights within the family. With respect to *Lily Thomas v. Union of India*⁷, the Supreme Court of India declared that in their father's estate, Christian women have equal property rights. This decision was a major victory for the rights of women in India. In addition, the judiciary has contributed to the advancement of women's involvement in public life. Within the case of *Indira Gandhi v. Raj Narain*⁸, the Supreme Court held that women are entitled to equal opportunities in employment. This judgment has paved the way for increased female involvement in the workforce. By interpreting as well applying that law in a way that protects and promotes women's rights, the judiciary has helped to create a more just and equitable society. Numerous laws have been created both domestically and internationally. But because of the male-dominated culture, women are also exploited. The significant contribution that India's judiciary makes to women's empowerment is examined in this research paper.

The Study's Purpose

The primary goal of the essay is to outline how India's constitutional rights and judicial system contribute to women's empowerment.

Legislative Measures for Women Empowerment in India

India has a plethora of laws designed to empower women in the areas of economic, social, legal, professional, and personal affairs. The fundamental law of India is the Constitution, which guarantees

equality for women. A few of the most important laws pertaining to women's empowerment should be mentioned.

Constitutional Provisions:

The Constitution of India guarantees gender equality and empowers women through various provisions:

1. Article 14: Ensures equality before the law and prohibits discrimination on the basis of sex.
2. Article 15(3): Empowers the state to make special provisions for women and children.
3. Article 16: Ensures equality of opportunity in public employment.
4. Article 21: Protects the right to life, which includes the right to live a life free from violence and discrimination.
5. At least one-third of the seats in Panchayats and Municipalities are reserved for women per the 73rd and 74th amendments to the Indian Constitution. Now, by the 108th Constitutional Amendment, 33% seats in the State Legislature and Parliament have been reserved for women.

Major Legislation for Women Empowerment:

1. The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961: Prohibits the giving or taking of dowry and provides for punishment for violators.
2. The Indian Penal Code (Section 498A): Makes cruelty to women by their husbands or other relatives a punishable offense.
3. The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973: Provides for special protection and procedures for women in criminal cases.
4. The Maternity Benefit Act, 1961: Provides for maternity leave and benefits to women employed in public and private sectors.
5. The Equal Remuneration Act, 1956: Prohibits discrimination in the payment of wages on the basis of sex.
6. The Hindu Marriage Act, 1955: Provides for polygamy and gives women equal rights in divorce and maintenance.
7. The Muslim Personal Law (Shariat) Application Act, 1937: Recognizes the right of Muslim women to maintenance, inheritance, and divorce under Muslim law.

Recent Initiatives for Women Empowerment:

1. The National Commission for Women (NCW): A statutory body responsible for protecting and promoting the rights of women.
2. The Women and Child Development Ministry: A ministry responsible for formulating and implementing policies for women and children.
3. The Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP) Scheme: A government scheme aimed at preventing female infanticide and promoting girl education.
4. The Sukanya Samridhi Yojana: A government scheme aimed at providing financial assistance to girls for their education and marriage.
5. The Employees State Insurance Act of 1948: This law gives working women insurance, mate 24. The 2005 Protection of Women against Domestic Abuse Act: This law offers legal support to those women's who are facing domestic abuse as well as penalties for husbands and his family members who perpetrate domestic violence. Additionally, it offers women interim maintenance as well as Indemnity and damages.⁹
6. The Indian Evidence Act of 1872, the Code of Criminal Procedures of 1973, and the provisions of sections 375, 376, 354, or 509 of the Indian Penal Code are amended to address sexual assault by the Act of 2013 amending the Criminal Law.
7. (The Criminal Law (Amendment) Ordinance, 2018) acted upon by government. The IPC, 1860, POCSO Act, 2012, and other legislation pertaining to female rape are amended by the Ordinance.

According to the POCSO Act, rape of minors would be punished under the POCSO Act's harsher penalty schedule than under the IPC.¹⁰

India has made significant progress in terms of legal provisions and initiatives for women empowerment. However, there is still a long way to go in achieving gender equality in practice.

Role of Judicial Activism in Empowering Women

Legislature creates laws, the executive branch carries them out, and the judiciary interprets them. However, in recent years, the judiciary has taken on a new function; it is now an active participant in the legal system rather than just an interpretation or a passive observer. Its new position has sparked a lot of discussion, but it is impossible to deny that it has benefited women in any way. Numerous laws and policies have been passed that greatly contribute to the empowerment of women. The court is demonstrating its faithfulness as the defender of constitutional guarantees in the present, when the other two branches of government have not fulfilled their respective roles. Additionally, it operates in accordance with international conventions.¹¹ The judiciary's ability to provide better and more compliant justice by going above and beyond the legislative limit was expanded by jurisprudence. Arthur Schlesinger Jr. coined the term "judicial activism" in an article titled "Fortune Magazine released a piece titled "The Supreme Court: 1947" in January 1947. A.M. Ahmadi contends that as the function's primary focus is the protection of the public interest, judicial activism is an essential adjunct of it. The judiciary is said to as the independent branch of government in our country¹².

The two roles of this Independent Judiciary-

1. The conventional role, which is to interpret the law;
2. Judicial activism, which is to go above and beyond the letter of the law and use the power of discretion to administer justice.

Historically, the main duty of the court has been to administer justice by interpreting laws and constitutional clauses. The structure of the courts that protects the rule of law is known as the judiciary, sometimes known as the judicature or judiciary. A strong agency is necessary to uphold the rule of law because it has no power on its own. Law's outcome is determined by the extent of its execution and the executor's skill. The significance of the word "judicial activism" has increased dramatically in the last few years. It might be characterized as a changing judicial viewpoint system inside a changing society.

The judiciary's contribution in granting women's identical rights

The Indian Supreme Court made a decision in the well-known leading case of *Randhir Singh v. Union of India*¹³ that although the concept of equal pay is not a constitutional requirement, it is unquestionably a desirable outcome. According to Constitutional Article 39(d), "equal pay for equal work is guaranteed to men and women." Similar to this, it was determined in *Grihakalyan v. Union of India*¹⁴ that denying equal pay for equal work constitutes an irrational classification in accordance with the Constitution's article 14. In this leading case of *Air India v. Nargesh Meerza*¹⁵, According to the court, it was unlawful to terminate a person's service due to pregnancy since it was unreasonable and arbitrary, as per Article 14. Particular rules for women and children are outlined in Article 15(3), while Equality of opportunity in relation to public employment is covered in Article 16. However, There isn't any clause or legislative bill that addresses safeguards against workplace sexual harassment, In order to do so in compliance with the law, the judiciary in *Vishakha v. State of Rajasthan*¹⁶ used its most potent and hidden weapon and established specific guidelines. Recent golden judgments from the thriving judiciary have elevated women's dignity. *Female Workers (Muster Roll) v. Municipal Corporation of Delhi*¹⁷, the Supreme Court decided to extend the Maternity Benefit Act, 1961's protections to Delhi Municipal Corporation's female Muster Roll (Daily Wagers) employees. In this case, the Court directly integrated the provisions of CEDAW, 1979's Article 11 into Indian law. In the leading case *Delhi Domestic Working Women's Forum v. Union of India*¹⁸, the Indian Supreme Court recommended creating a section for compensating victims of rape at the moment the offender was found guilty is sentenced to prison.

The court suggested that the victim receive pain compensation from the Criminal Injury Remuneration Board or the court if childbirth results from rape, suffering, and shock as well as for any lost wages resulting from pregnancy and childbirth expenses. The Indian Court established guidelines in this case *Gourav Jain v. Union of India*¹⁹, which included the requirement, of giving advice, bribing, and pressuring the women to quit prostitution and look for other jobs. In *Sakshi v. Union of India*²⁰, the Indian Court acknowledged the rape law's shortcomings and recommended that legislators make the necessary changes. Criminal Amendment Act, 2013 was passed on the basis of these suggestions, and it became operative on 3 February 2013. The quartet of accused in the gang-rape case in Delhi from December 16, 2012 were recently given capital punishment by the Court of Delhi on September 13, 2013, stating that the severity of the offense cannot be tolerated, acting as a deterrent in The seriousness of the crime is intolerable, serving as a disincentive to society.²¹

Concluding words

As a result, the court rulings made by courts of India show the judiciary's proactive role plays in defending female against mistreatment at a point when law enforcement is meted out sparsely and uniforms are used. The judiciary can "definitely go further mere legality shielding women against injustices experienced due to biological and sociological elements," even though it cannot replace the legislation. A number of elements come together to make up justice: laws that are enacted in response to the shifting demands of society, are effectively enforced, and are interpreted and applied in a progressive and proactive manner to fill in any gaps left by statutory enactments. What matters is not merely the law, but the law in action.²⁴ Therefore, a crucial element that could contribute to the fair and effective administration of justice is a sensitive judiciary—a court that takes a comprehensive approach to the issue and its circumstances. Depending on their upbringing, judges also have their own philosophies and convictions. Individual inhibitions and predispositions are not accepted in the collaborative qualitative philosophy of justice dispensation, though.

Judge Lahotian proposed that judges should remember the following guidelines to accomplish gender justice in his remarks at the book launch for "Search for a Vision Statement on Women Empowerment vis-...-vis Legislation and Judicial Decisions," which was written by the National Commission for Women and released by the Indian Trust for Innovation and Social Change.

- (1) Understand the cultural and historical context where women have resided throughout history and take into consideration theirs as a class needs;
- (2) Since women comprise the weaker social groups, approach gender-related issues and situations in a way that treats the weaker members of society fairly and instills confidence in them; and
- (3) Give women confidence and treat them with honor and dignity in them as victims or justice seekers through your conduct, behavior, and ideology.
- (4) Don't let them be harassed, and don't do anything that could be construed as harassing a woman.
- (5) Try to provide a victim of a woman with prompt, efficient, affordable, and true justice.

Conclusion

It is ultimately possible to draw the conclusion that there are many laws protecting the rights and advantages of women. But those laws can't be fully enforced because of illiteracy and ignorance. The goal of India's several laws is to empower women. The court decisions made by Indian courts show the judiciary's proactive involvement in shielding women from exploited at a point when laws are uniformed because there is insufficient enforcement apparatus. As the defender of the nation's fundamental laws, it makes an effort to interpret laws in line with the values outlined in the Indian Constitution. Given that society and social structures are dynamic rather than static, interpretations must adapt to keep up with these changes. The establishment of this function of the judiciary is the result of the corrupt system; in a democratic society where the other two branches failed miserably, the court continued to be the people's final hope. It attempts to give women in the socioeconomic environment justice by exercising its discretionary power. P.N. Bhagwati, Judge correctly stated, "The judge infuses life and blood into the dry skeleton provided by the legislature and creates a living

organism appropriate and adequate to meet the needs of the society." Women are now in a better position in society as a result of both legislative and judicial actions. However, in India, a woman must go great distances to attain 100% empowerment.

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